

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B173
Date: 14 Feb 2006
Take Off: 09:49:53
Landing: 14:36:15
Flight Time: 4h46m22s

Campaign: DODO
Trials Instructions: Biomass / Aerosol Sampling
Operating Area: North of Dakar, over ocean

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Alan Roberts	Directflight
3	CCM	Jackie Mulholland	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist	Ellie Highwood	Reading University
5	Flight Manager	Ruth Purvis	FAAM
6	VACC / PAN / WAS	Jim McQuaid	University of Leeds
7	AVAPS / CCM2	Paul James	FAAM
8	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office
9	Filters	Claire McConnell	Reading University
10	AMS	Paul Williams	University of Manchester
11	Wet Neph	James Bowles	Met Office
12	Core Chemistry	Alan Woolley	FAAM
13	SWS / SHIMS	Ian Rule	Met Office
14	ARIES	Alan Vance	Met Office
15	Mission Scientist 2	Ben Johnson	Met Office
16	CVI / CCN	Jamie Trembath	FAAM
17			
18			

Flight Track:

B173 Track 14-FEB-06

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b173
 Date: 14 Feb 2006
 Project: DODO
 Location: DAKAR

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
093630		taxy	0.03 kft	154	
093754		ASP	0.04 kft	105	From Dakar
094953		T/O	0.01 kft	353	From Dakar
094953	100857	Profile 1	0.93 - 19.0 kft	009	1000ft/min
095500		Tapes started	5.6 kft	008	
100908		sonde 1	19.0 kft	355	
101014	103251	Profile 2	19.0 - 50ft	355	
101306		qnh 1010	16.9 kft	356	
102631		descent change	3.0 kft	013	500 ft/min
103449	104950	Run 1	100 ft	191	
105131	105633	Profile 3	100 ft - 2.5 kft	354	
105621	111125	Run2	2.5 kft	004	
111308	111452	Profile 4	2.5 - 4.0 kft	184	
111452	112456	Run 3	4000 kft	184	
112753	113009	Profile 5	4.0 - 2.5 kft	067	@1000ft/min
113009	114353	Run 4	2.5 kft	067	
113113		changed tapes	2.5 kft	067	
113543		UFC changed to DFC	2.5 kft	073	
113745		ship track	2.5 kft	073	2500 ft
114427	114650	Profile 6.1	2.4 kft - 500ft	074	1000ft/min reduce to 500ft @ 1000ft
114650	115057	Profile 6.2	500ft - 5.0 kft	079	1000ft min-1 reduce to 500ft @ 1000ft
115057	115606	Profile 6.3	5.0 - 500ft	076	
115606	115709	Profile 6.4	0.5 - 1.5 kft	074	
120119	120602	Run 5	1.5kft	075	1500ft @ 120119
120309	120429	Profile 7	0.55 - 0.58 kft	262	
120429	121142	Run 6	500ft	266	
121236	121854	Run 6.2	1.5 kft	263	
121910	122333	Profile 8	1.5 - 5.0 kft	264	
124037	124330	Profile 9	5.0 - 2.5 kft	197	
124555	124625	Run 7	2.4 - 2.0 kft	066	
124625	124821	Profile 10	1.7 - 0.83 kft	080	
124835			0.84 kft	093	repositioning
125106	131808	Run 8	1.5 kft	017	
130433		tapes changed	1.3 kft	014	
132011	133713	Run 9	1.5 kft	189	
132351		Event	1.3 kft	173	16N57.64 16W 12.63 lots of aerosol
133858	134103	Profile 11	1.2 - 50 ft	006	
134251	134837	Profile 12	1.9 - 9.0 kft	021	strarted at minima
135019	135525	Profile 12	9.0 - 16.0 kft	202	
135532		sonde 2	16.0 kft	208	
135834		Event	16.0 kft	208	End of science
142402		asp	15.7 kft	209	asp closed
143615		Land	0.08 kft	352	14:36:15
144622		final position gps	0.08 kft	337	14'44.56N 17'29.30W

B173 Track 14-FEB-06

GOOY -> GQNN - Overview

NavData Cycle 2006-1 Expires: Thursday, 16 February 2006.

Scale: 1:2453718 (1 inch = 33.65 naut mi). Printed on 13 Feb 2006

JEPPESEN

FliteStar 9.150

FAAM Sortie Brief

DODO Flight: In situ sampling of dust from Western Sahara sources

Flight No: B173

Date: 14th February 2006

Objectives:

1. In-situ sampling of Saharan dust outflow over the ocean.
2. In-situ sampling of dust over the land produced from local sources
3. Possible characterisation of surface radiative properties and radiation measurement from above dust layers.

Location: Over ocean North of Dakar, and across Western parts of Mauritania.

NULET: 18 25N 17 13W

LIMAX : 16 45N 17 20W

ARIKO: 17 12N 14 50 W

A: 20N 15W

Weather: Likely to be considerable cirrus over entire operating region.

Special requirements: Low-level (50ft) flying over ocean, drop-sonde over ocean north of Dakar.

Flight pattern:

1. Take off from Dakar. Open air sample pipes on runway.
2. Profile ascent to FL200 on a heading towards NULET, 500ft/min below 3000ft, 1000ft/min above 3000ft. Prepare for dropsonde launch during ascent and drop at the commencement of the profile [25 mins, T= 25 mins].
3. Profile descent from FL200 to 50ft at 1000ft/min above 3000ft and 500ft/min below 3000ft [23 mins, T=48mins].
4. Ascend to 100ft and turn onto reciprocal heading [2mins, T=50 mins].
5. SLR for 15 mins from NULET towards LIMAX at 100ft, SWS & ARIES point down to characterise ocean surface properties [15 mins, T=65 mins].
6. Broken profile ascent from 100ft to FL030 (or altitude corresponding to the middle of the dust layer) at 500ft/min [10 mins, T=75mins], returning to LIMAX.
7. SLR from point B towards NULET (within middle of dust layer) [15 mins, T=90 mins].
8. Broken profile ascent from FL030 to FL080 (or an altitude just above the dust layer) at 1000ft/min, returning to NULET, SWS & ARIES pointing down to characterise radiative effect of dust [10 mins, T=100mins].
9. SLR from NULET towards LIMAX at FL080 (or just above dust layer) [15 mins, T=115].
10. Turn onto eastwards heading towards ARIKO over Western Mauritania, and profile descent at 1000ft/min to FL040 or level to be determined [5 mins, 120 mins].
11. SLR for 10 mins at FL040 or level to be determined by mission scientist [10 mins, T=130 mins].
12. Perform a saw-tooth profile ascent and descent from FL040 to FL080, and back down to FL020, arriving at ARIKO [15 mins, T=145 mins].
13. Turn onto northwards heading towards point A and SLR to point A at lowest safe altitude, SWS & ARIES pointing down to characterise surface [30 mins, 175 mins].
14. Turn onto reciprocal heading and SLR from point A to ARIKO at a level to be determined by mission scientist [30 mins, T=205 mins].
15. Turn onto westward heading and perform SLR or saw-tooths at levels within the dust plume [30 mins, T= 235 mins].
16. SLR from LIMAX to Dakar at level(s) to be determined [40 mins, T=275 mins].
17. Land at Dakar [T=275mins / 4hrs 25 mins].

Sortie Debrief

Flight Number: B173

Date: 14th February 2006

Sortie Objectives: In-situ sampling of Saharan dust outflow over the ocean; in-situ sampling of Saharan dust over the land produced from local sources.

Operating area: Over ocean North of Dakar, and across Western Parts of Mauritania between:

NULET 18 25N, 17 13 W; LIMAX: 16 45 N 17 20 W; ARIKO: 17 12 N 14 50 W and A 20 N 15 W.

Weather: Considerable cirrus (7/8) throughout. Very windy at ground level in Dakar.

Flight Patterns:

After take off from Dakar, a profile ascent to the North to FL190 showed reasonable scattering at the surface, a layer with larger particles around 2500ft and clean air above 5000ft. Layers with elevated CO and ozone occurred between FL135 and FL160 but there was no aerosol signal. A sonde was launched successfully. A profile descent to 50ft in the direction of NULET (approximately north of Dakar) revealed slightly different structure with no evidence of previous dust like layer. Sea salt was present at low levels, consistent with sea state. An SLR at 100ft provided more sampling opportunities for sea salt. ARIES and SWS spent time looking both up and down during these SLRs, although the usefulness of this data is questionable due to the high levels of cloud. Towards the south of the operating region a turn was made, and an SLR performed at 2500ft. No sign of previously seen large particles at this level, and scattering remained low. Same story on the return leg at 4000ft.

At southern end, turned towards coastline. Switched recording cameras to forward and down. SWS and ARIES looking down. Profiled down to 2500ft to intercept coast. 2 minutes after crossing coast, a brief plume of large particles was seen. Ozone also dropped consistent with ozone removal on dust. This signal did not persist in land during the saw tooth between 500ft and FL500. Visibility generally good, many goats and Bedouin tents present. Surface sparsely vegetated.

Due to lack of dust, a decision was made to terminate run and an SLR at 500ft made towards the position of the dust source previously identified. Due to general discomfort, the run height was raised to 1500ft. The same plume was briefly evident. A 10 minute holding pattern at FL050 over the ocean due west of this point was maintained to allow people to get more comfortable and as a Valentine's day gift from Ellie. Subsequently, a descent to 2500ft along the same track back along the coast line was made, and then a descent to 1500ft and a turn to head into the wind once the dust source was reached. An SLR at 1500ft following the wind was performed for 30 minutes along the coastline to Nouatchokk. Large particles, scattering up to above $600 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^{-1}$ for most of this run. Ozone depleted. Some structure in scattering and ozone near the city of Nouatchok itself. The scattering dropped slightly to north of Nouatchok but was still several $100 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^{-1}$. A turn was made at our most northerly possible point, and a further 10 minute run back down wind at 1500ft within the dust plume completed. SWS was looking up, but again, the usefulness of this is questionable. Slant visibility only around 3-4 nm.

When visibility improved (scattering $400 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^{-1}$) the plane turned north again and descended to 50ft along the coastline (good views of dunes and surf zone). A profile

ascent was performed to FL150 heading North. Dust contained below 4500ft. Clear air above that, well defined top visually. Cirrus above. A sonde was launched successfully above the dust layer. Science ended at FL160 and transit home was completed. On approach to Dakar, visibility improved dramatically. An elevated dark layer over land was visible, possibly consistent with biomass forecasts.

Summary:

The first half of the flight was frustrating. However, a strong dust plume was found, good in-situ samples taken. Possibly the dust flight of the campaign.

Problems

No wet neph for all bar last 10 minutes of flight.
ARIES operator ill during flight.

Ellie Highwood

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.173**.....

Date **14 Feb 2006** ♥

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
0930				Dakar	7/8 mid → high level cloud
					>60% RH, winds
	T/O				T/O to North Sea state 2-3 haze
094953	PI ↑	1000ft/min			Visibility reduced
	to FL190	4000ft			Clearer str above, cloud above
					~7/8 Ci + some slightly low.
					FL190
					clean air here
					CO ₂ O ₃ signal FL135 FL160
					remnants of biomass, no aerosol signal.
					green red scat more
					2 1/2
					50 100
					extensive cloud ahead
100857	A end	FL190			
100908	Sonde				Sonde drop ①
101014	P2 ↓	FL190 ↓			Descent
					Sea state 3
103251	P2 ^{end}	50ft			Considerable white foam, waves
10344.3	R21	100ft			Sea salt some slightly elevated
					NO _x values in bottom
					visibility reduced to land side (sun)
					2000ft.
					SWS & ARIES ↑ for 1st 1/2, swap
					@ 1043 to ↓
					↑ in scat → 130 m ⁻¹ red > blue
					towards Limel, suggest sea salt
					Blue drops out S of Limel so
					even larger S of Limel

2500ft
FL190
3500ft

R

LIMAX → to coast
2500ft

Mission Scientist's Log

Men sawtooth
2500ft → 500ft towards Arica

Flight No **B.173**

Date 14/2/06

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
104950	R1	100ft			End run
105131	P3	100ft ↑			Start profile to F 2500ft
105621	P3	FL2500ft			
105621	R2	2500ft			Background aerosol run.
111125	R2	2500ft			end run
111308	P4	2500ft ↑			
111452	P4	4000ft			Profile end cloud above
111452	R3	4000ft			short run → nothing much going on.
112753	P5	4000ft ↓			Profile down
113009	R4	2500ft			Cameras swapped. SWS ↓
114353	R4end				Oreland end of run
114887	P6.1	2500ft ↓			Sawtooth's down. Some haze
114650	P6.1 P6.2	500ft ↑			Visibility down. Dust?
115057	P6.3	FL050 ↓			Near coast O ₃ down, neph
115606	P6.3 P6.4				scatt suggests dust. Zwin
115709	P6.4 R5				
	R5 P7				
120429	P7 R6.1	500ft			hole in Cirrus ahead.
121142		↑			Sparse vegetation @ surface
121236	R6.2	1500ft			Recommence run
121854	R6.2	1500ft			Out over coast for comfert
121910	P8	1800ft ↑			break.
124037	P9	FL050 ↓			
124313	P9end	2500ft			

Mission Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.173**.....

 Date 14/2/06.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
1	R7/P10.1				1500ft
125106	R8	1500ft			SWS ↓ Dust! SWS up Scattering 300m ⁻¹ Scattering up to 600m ⁻¹ Visibility dramatically reduced Strong gradients 1000cm ⁻¹ Following plume approx along coastline but slightly off.
131354					Neph drops, a CO structure passing Nantohok to RHS Some O ₃ correlation
131808	R8	end run 1500ft			Plume dropping off towards NWS moving away from coast
132011	R9	1500ft			Passing Nantohok Start vis 3-4 nm
133713	R9				end run, sea 400 m ⁻¹ Broken profile
133858	P11	1500ft ↓			Descent to 50ft over surf zone due to visibility
134103		50ft			Ascent to
134305	P12	50ft ↑			Ascent to FL150
		FL050			Top of layer vis
134847	P12	FL090			Profile interupt. Cirrus above
135019	P12	FL090 ↑			Recommence P

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B173

Date: 14/02/06	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 08:20:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 1 of 4
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
09:49:53																Start Profile 1 from Take-off	
09:52:43	60	0.10	Off	10	2											FL030	
09:53:36	75	0.09	Off	5	1											FL040	
09:54:34	6	0.09	Off													FL050	
09:55:26	3	0.09	Off													FL060	
09:56:28	9	0.10	Off													FL070	
09:57:21	23	0.08	Off													FL080	
09:58:31	10	0.10	Off													FL090	
09:59:40	15	0.11	Off													FL100	
10:00:39	18	0.13	Off													FL110	
10:01:40	10	0.10	Off													FL120	
10:02:43	10	0.10	Off													FL130	
10:03:50	10	0.10	Off													FL140	
10:04:55	10	0.10	Off													FL150	
10:06:03	8	0.10	Off													FL160	
10:07:08	3	0.13	Off													FL170	
10:07:59	4	0.15	Off													FL180	
10:08:55	6	0.11	Off													End of Profile 1 @ FL190	
10:10:14																Start Profile 2 from FL190	
10:12:58	10	0.10	Off													FL170	
10:14:27	20	0.09	Off													FL150	
10:16:09	25	0.08	Off													FL130	
10:17:04	15	0.09	Off													FL120	
10:18:00	20	0.08	Off													FL110	
10:19:06	28	0.09	Off													FL100	
10:20:11	20	0.09	Off													FL090	
10:21:19	8	0.10	Off													FL080	
10:22:20	5	0.09	Off													FL070	
10:23:16	10	0.09	Off													FL060	
10:24:16	80	0.10	Off	10	2											FL050	
10:25:15	190	0.10	Off	10	2											FL040	
10:26:18	230	0.09	Off	10	2											FL030	
10:28:02	170	0.10	Off	10	2											FL020	
10:30:15	170	0.11	Off	20	3											FL010	
10:32:53	200	0.11	Off	70	8											End of Profile 2 @ 50'	
10:34:43																Start Run 1 @ 100'	
10:35:00	180	0.12	Off	80	10												
10:37:00	190	0.11	Off	90	10												
10:39:00	185	0.12	Off	90	8												
10:41:00	170	0.12	Off	90	10												
10:43:00	170	0.12	Off	90	11												
10:45:00	175	0.13	Off	100	12												
10:47:00	190	0.13	Off	100	11												
10:49:00	195	0.15	Off	100	15												
10:49:51																End of Run 1	
10:51:33																Start Profile 3 from	

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B173

Date: 14/02/06	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 08:20:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 2 of 4
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
10:52:53	190	0.11	Off	10	3											1000'	
10:56:18																End of Profile 3 & Start Run 2 @ 2500'	
10:57:00	240	0.10	Off	10	2												
10:59:00	200	0.10	Off	10	2												
11:01:00	165	0.10	Off	10	1												
11:03:00	140	0.10	Off	10	2												
11:05:00	140	0.10	Off	10	2												
11:07:00	140	0.10	Off	10	1												
11:09:00	120	0.10	Off	10	2												
11:11:00	100	0.10	Off	10	2												
11:11:27																End of Run 2	
11:13:10																Start Profile 4 from 2500'	
11:13:56	100	0.11	Off	10	2											3000'	
11:14:54																End of Profile 4 & Start Run 3 @ 4000'	
11:15:00	140	0.10	Off	10	1												
11:17:00	165	0.10	Off	10	1												
11:19:00	190	0.10	Off	10	2												
11:21:00	190	0.10	Off	10	2												
11:23:00	190	0.09	Off	10	2												
11:24:56																End of Run 3	
11:27:55																Start Profile 5 from 4000'	
11:28:59	210	0.10	Off	10	2											3000'	
11:30:10																End of Profile 5 & Start Run 4 @ 2000'	
11:31:00	255	0.10	Off	10	3												
11:33:00	230	0.10	Off	10	2												
11:35:00	260	0.10	Off	10	2												
11:37:00	260	0.10	Off	10	2												
11:39:00	260	0.10	Off	10	2												
11:41:00	250	0.10	Off	10	2												
11:43:00	230	0.09	Off	10	2												
11:43:53																End of Run 5 & Start Profile 6.1 from 2000'	
11:45:52	260	0.10	Off	20	8											1000'	
11:46:52	290	0.10	Off	30	8											End of Profile 6.1 & start Profile 6.2 @ 500'	
11:47:39	250	0.10	Off	30	7											1000'	
11:48:29	190	0.10	Off	10	7											2000'	
11:49:30	170	0.09	Off	10	8											3000'	
11:50:12	165	0.09	Off	10	8											4000'	
11:50:58	45	0.11	Off	10	2											End of Profile 6.2 & start Profile 6.3 @ 5000'	
11:51:56	170	0.10	Off	10	2											4000'	
11:53:01	220	0.09	Off	10	2											3000'	
11:54:04	270	0.09	Off	15	5											2000'	
11:55:10	270	0.10	Off	15	8											1000'	
11:56:05	260	0.10	Off	15	8											End of Profile 6.3 & Start Profile 6.4 @ 500'	
11:57:09																End of Profile 6.4 & Start Run 5 @ 1500'	
11:58:00	240	0.10	Off	20	8												
12:00:00	240	0.10	Off	20	3												

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B173

Date: 14/02/06	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 08:20:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 3 of 4
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
12:01:18																End of Run 5	
12:03:09																Start Profile 7 from 1500'	
12:04:30																End of Profile 7 & Start Run 6.1 @ 300'	
12:05:00	250	0.10	Off	20	10												
12:07:00	280	0.10	Off	20	10												
12:09:00	250	0.10	Off	30	8												
12:11:00	260	0.10	Off	30	8												
12:11:44																End of Run 6.1	
12:12:35																Start Run 6.2 @ 1500'	
12:13:00	280	0.10	Off	30	8												
12:15:00	245	0.10	Off	20	7												
12:17:00	265	0.10	Off	20	5												
12:18:56																End of Run 6.2 & Start Profile 8 from 1500'	
12:19:59	210	0.09	Off	20	3											FL020	
12:21:06	170	0.09	Off	10	2											FL030	
12:22:22	140	0.09	Off	10	2											FL040	
12:23:33	135	0.09	Off	15	3											End of Profile 8 @ FL050	
12:40:38	110	0.09	Off	10	3											Start Profile 9 from FL050	
12:41:35	220	0.09	Off	10	2											FL040	
12:42:39	210	0.10	Off	10	Noise											FL030	
12:43:27	250	0.10	Off	10	Noise											End of Profile 9 @ 2500'	
12:45:55																Start Run 7 @ 2500'	
12:46:29																End of Run 7 & Start Profile 10.1 from 2500'	
12:47:52	280	0.10	Off	20												1000'	
12:48:20																End of Profile 10.1 @ 700'	
12:51:06																Start Run 8 @ 1500'	
12:52:00	250	0.11	Off	40	10												
12:54:00	270	0.12	Off	100	Noise	1											
12:56:00	230	0.12	Off	100	30												
12:58:00	250	0.12	Off	100	Noise	1											
13:00:00	320	0.14	Off	120	Noise	1											
13:02:00	340	0.14	Off	150	Noise	2											
13:04:00	335	0.16	Off	200	Noise	5	200										
13:06:00	420	0.17	Off	300	100	6	300										
13:08:00	460	0.17	Off	400	100	7	100										
13:10:00	500	0.16	0	400	80	7	100										
13:12:00	400	0.16		200	70	7	100										
13:14:00	400	0.15		300	100	5	100										
13:16:00	440	0.14	Off	300	90	5	100										
13:18:07																End of Run	
13:20:13																Start Run 9 @ 1500'	
13:21:00	400	0.15	Off	300	100	5	100										
13:23:00	390	0.15	Off	200	80	5	100										
13:25:00	400	0.13	Off	200	80	3	100										
13:27:00	530	0.17	Off	300	100	6	100										
13:29:00	480	0.17	Off	500	100	5	100										

CLLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B173

Date:

B) FFSSP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to PC Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt	-	<u>NOT CARRIED OUT: FFSSP SWITCHED OFF FOR ALL BUT 2 MINS OF THE FLIGHT.</u>
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to the directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS		
3) RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Path name: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: 0 if unknown e) End time: 240000 if unknown		
4) RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: Use the most recent calibration file. Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP] f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)		Note the calibration file used Yes only if gross errors occur in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour
5) In PVWAVE a) enter: !path=!path+',mrfb:[pms.proc]' Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important! b) write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX','pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp',/auto 1st argument is output file from 5) 2nd argument is the MFD 3rd argument is the new FFSSP data file in M5 format c) exit		Note the correction applied to FFSSP time by /auto
6) MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: Enter updated MFD name d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default		
7) CHECKS:		
i) FFSSP and JW/Nevzorov LWC – are they correctly synchronized in time?		
ii) If not, may be necessary to repeat 5b) using addt=x keyword. This adds x sec to FFSSP time.		
iii) Alternative at 5b) is to use ,auto=602 or auto=605 to align FFSSP with Nevzorov LWC or TWC.		

CLLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B173

Date:

C) 2D PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer Bnnn.dat file from CD/DVD to PC	X	
2) Zip up file on PC (Bnnn.zip)	X	
3) FTP the zipped file (binary) from the PC to the directory SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] on FLOODS	X X	
4) Log on to FLOODS	X	Condor
5) unzip SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.zip	X	
6) In PVWAVE	X	Note the number of bad block reads and/or final numbers of blocks read & written
i) !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]'	X	
ii) CONVERT_SEADAS_FILE	X	Zero bad blocks
a) Input file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.dat	X	36336 blocks written
b) Output file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] Bnnn_seadas.dat		
iii) exit	X	
7) run MRFB:[PMS.SEADAS]READM200_FILE	X	Don't worry about lots of FORTRAN run-time errors as long as the program continues. These are format errors when writing to ascii files.
a) Default directory: PMSDATA:	X	
b) Flight number: Bnnn	X	
c) Disk file name: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] Bnnn_seadas.dat	X	
d) Comment string:	X	
e) Start time: 0 if unknown	X	
f) End time: 240000 if unknown	X	
g) Read 2DC: Y	X	
h) Read 2DP: Y	X	
i) Secondary data Y	X	
j) FSP-SYNC: Y	X	
k) cmd.str: Y	X	
l) Auto time correction: N	X	
m) Full length secondary: N	X	
8) 2D image display and printing		This section is optional Features to look for: 1) Noise on 2D-P – does it affect non-edge diodes (with potential to create spurious particle counts)? 2) Can you identify a dominant particle habit for the whole flight (eg. drops or crystals) 3)
Quick look at image blocks if required		
In PVWAVE		
i) !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]'		
i) WAVE> IMAGEDISPLAY		
a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA:		
b) Flight number: Bnnn		
c) IWC plot: N		
d) Select probe: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP		
e) Start time: 0 if unknown		
f) End time: 240000 if unknown		
g) Time interval (sec): 0 for every image block nominal 5 sec		

Preparation of imagery for Core data product		
iii) WAVE> auto_image a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Enter date: YYYYMMDD d) Enter start time 0 if unknown e) Enter end time 240000 if unknown f) Enter time interval (sec) between successive imaged blocks <p style="text-align: center;">10</p> iv) exit PVWAVE Creates files	PMSDATA:	FAAM_YYYYMMDD_R0_Bnnn_2Dx-IMAGES.PS
ftp *.PS files from PMSDATA: to PC		
Load each into Ghostview or other pdf-converter		
Output as pdf file (70 dpi resolution) and append name prefix of CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files		
9) run MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) File generation: Hit enter d) Time correction: Time offset of the 2D data e) TAS: Y f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both <p style="text-align: center;">0 unless either probe known to be faulty</p> h) Start time: Take-off or 0 if unknown i) End time: Landing or 240000 if unknown j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5 k) Particle type: 8 if known to be in ice cloud <p style="text-align: center;">11 if known to be in water cloud 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown</p> l) Coefficient choice: 2 m) Output root filename: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROC2D	<u>NO DATA !!!</u>	If program crashes at a certain Time, for any reason, re-run With that time as the new end. Look for realistic times in Flight Summary file or Cloud Phys operator log. Note the particle type
10) In PVWAVE i) enter: !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important! ii) WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:BNNN_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:BNNN_M5PROC2D' iii) exit	<u>NO DATA !!!</u>	Note: This will run quicker if you specify correct start / end times at 9h) and 9j).
11) MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proc2D b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: Enter modified MFD name d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default	<u>NO DATA !!!</u>	
12) CHECKS:		
i) Is 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC?		

CLLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B173

Date:

D) PCASP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Complete stage 7) in 2D processing	X	
Ensures Bnnn_FSP.DAT containing raw PCASP data is written to directory PMSDATA:	X X	
2) run MRFB:[PMS.PCASP]PROCPCASP_NEW	X	Note the min size channel
a) Flight number: Bnnn	X	Note the volume flow rate
b) File name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_FSP.DAT	X	
c) Root output name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP	X	
Produces PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.DAT (binary)	X	
PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.OUT (ascii)	X	
d) Minimum size channel: Default = 1	X	Bin 1 chosen
If smallest size channel are known to be noisy the value of the highest noise free channel to be entered here	X X	
e) Calibration volume flow rate: Use the most recent value.	X	
Calibration files to be stored in ?????	X	
Entering zero gives default value = 1.0 cm ³ /sec	X	1.6 ml/sec
f) Time correction: Same value as used in 2D processing stage 9 d)	X	
g) Start time: Take-off or 0 if unknown	X	Look for realistic times in Flight Summary file or Cloud Phys operator log.
h) End time: Landing or 240000 if unknown	X	
3) In PVWAVE	X	Note: This will run quicker if you specify correct start / end times at 2g) and 2h).
i) enter:	X	
!PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]'	X	
Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important!	X	
ii) write_procpcasp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procpcasp.dat'	X	
,'pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp'	X	
iii) exit	X	
4) MODIFY	X	
a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp	X	
b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX	X	
c) New dataset: Enter modified MFD name	X	
d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default	X	

CLLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B173

Date:

E) NetCDF file preparation and ftp to BADC				
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments		
1) Run TAREXEC:MFD_BADC				
For inputs below, just press ENTER to use defaults				
a) MFD to convert: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX b) version number for BADC: r[0] c) Names file: TARDIS_ROOT:[CALTEXT.NETCDF]CP_NAMES.TXT d) Directory: [DATA_ROOT:[NETCDF]] e) File prefix: [core-cloud-phy_faam] f) File suffix: [] g) File for output: [core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_rm_Bnnn.nc]		Defaults in [square brackets] As from 4c) above default NOT the default default default default Default name is generated		
2) Ftp transfer to BADC				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - stage 1) creates two files: - core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_rm_Bnnn.nc - core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_rm_Bnnn.txt The *.txt file should be renamed to core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_rm_Bnnn_descrip.txt but this cannot be done on VMS as the filename is too long You should do it if the file is first transferred to a PC, or after it has been uploaded to the appropriate "incoming" directory at BADC a) ftp ftp.badc.rl.ac.uk b) login with username and password c) cd /incoming/faam/campaign-processed-core d) copy *.txt file as ascii e) copy *.nc and *2D-IMAGES.pdf files as binary				

F) BACKUP PROCEDURES		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Backup the intermediate files created in PMSDATA:		
a) zip "-V" PMSDATA:Bnnn*. * outdir:Bnnn_PMSDATA.zip Note that the uppercase "-V" option is important to preserve the VMS file characteristics when files are restored from this zip file.		Note destination directory "outdir"

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG**Flight number:** Bnnn**Date:** DD/MM/YY

A) Raw data transfer to BADC		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer raw data files from DVD to PC Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt Bnnn_FFSSP.raw Bnnn_FFSSP_House_1.hse etc.		
2) Zip these file on the PC -output file: core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_r0_bnnn_rawffssp.zip		
3) Transfer SEADAS Bnnn.dat file from CD/DVD to PC		
4) Zip up file on PC (Bnnn.zip) - rename Bnnn.zip to core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_r0_bnnn_rawseadas.zip		
5) ftp to BADC a) ftp ftp.badc.rl.ac.uk b) login with username and password c) cd incoming/faam/campaign_raw d) bin e) put core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_r0_bnnn_rawffssp.zip f) put core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_r0_bnnn_rawseadas.zip		Binary data transfer

CCN LOG

ALLEVIATOR		HEIGHT	TEMP INLET	STATIC					REMARKS
ON	OFF			1	2	3	4	5	
10:35:05	35:41	100ft	19.97	0.18	0.33	0.5	4.25	5.5	Run 1
			19.15	304	371				aborted.
				220	258				
				2306	2299				
				1070.1	1019.1				
10:56:21	10:57:00	250ft	19.56	0.18	0.33	0.53			Run 2
			18.77	297	437	475			aborted
			17.87	213	203	193			smoking coming out
				2337	2370	2412			pellets for temp
				1016.5	1016.5	1016.7			Settings
11:14:55	11:15:36	400ft	19.38	0.18	0.33	0.51	0.75	1.14	Run 3
			18.66	240	339	594	822	985	
			17.9	172	172	192	192	228	
			17.2	2340	2371	2397	2417	2447	Value
			16.17	1014.4	1014.3	1014.3	1014.3	1014.2	shaking?
11:30:20	11:30:56	250ft	19.98	0.18	0.34	0.52	0.76	1.11	
			19.22	382	403	672	720	972	DT ↓ long
			18.55	215	212	221	227	262	Shab time
			17.79	2370	2352	2338	2326	2326	
			16.81	1016.4	1016.3	1016.3	1016.3	1016.3	Run 4.
11:38:48	11:39:23	"	20.21	0.18	0.33	0.5	0.75		aborted
			19.51	337	474	674	726		end of
			18.45	203	200	195	195		Run 4
			17.9	2312	2316	2326	2334		
				1016.2	1016.1	1016.2	1016.1		
11:57:14	11:57:50	1500	20.97	0.18					Run 5
				284					aborted.
				217					
				2434					
				1016.2					
12:04:28	12:05:00	500ft	20.94	0.2	0.33	0.5	4.25	5.5	Run 6
			20.27	337	538	742			aborted
			19.95	192	264	288			
				2337	2326	2318			
				1016.3	1016.4	1016.4			
12:51:37	12:52:13		22.49						
				262					
				2445					
				1016.2					

NO3 123
 SO4 114
 O2 gases 718
 1.453 ↑
 19 2
 6162
 0.086
 1.16
 1.13

Filter Sampling Log

Flight No:

B173

Date:

14 FEB 2006

Operator:

Type of filters mounted in	Top inlet	47 mm Whatman QMA (top)	Bottom inlet	90 mm 0.4 µm Nuclepore followed by a 90 mm paper (top)
Except for				

Run No	Disk #1 TOP	Disk #2 MIDDLE	Disk #3 BOTTOM	Inlet Top/ Bottom	Time On	Time Off	Flight Run	Accum Vol [l]	Comments
Filters run1	B173Q11	----	----	Top	10:34:49	10:49:50	R1	2250	100 feet
Filters run1	B173N3	----	----	Bottom	10:34:49	10:49:50	R1	1545	100 feet
Filters run2	B173Q10	----	----	Top	10:56:00	11:11:25	R2	2116	2500 feet
Filters run2	B173N9	----	----	Bottom	10:56:00	11:11:25	R2	1563	2500 feet
Filters run3	B173Q4	----	----	Top	11:15:55	11:24:56	R3	1718	4000 feet
Filters run3	B173N6	----	----	Bottom	11:15:55	11:24:56	R3	958	4000 feet
Filters run4	B173Q5	----	----	Top	11:57:37	12:18:54	R5/P7/R6/R6.2	3092	Run interrupted + cut short, filter left in for reciprocal run at lower level. R5 = 1.5 kft P7 = 0.55–0.58 kft R6 = 500ft R6.2 = 1.5 kft
Filters run4	B173N5	----	----	Bottom	11:57:37	12:18:54	R5/P7/R6/R6.2	2191	Run interrupted + cut short, filter left in for reciprocal run at lower level. R5 = 1.5 kft P7 = 0.55–0.58 kft R6 = 500ft R6.2 = 1.5 kft
Filters run5	B173Q3	----	----	Top	12:51:06	13:37:13	R8/R9	6263	1500 feet in dust
Filters run5	B173N10	----	----	Bottom	12:51:06	13:37:13	R8/R9	4451	1500 feet in dust

ARIES flight log

Flight: B173

Location: N & Dakar

page 1 of 4

Date: 14-2-6

Operator(s): VANCE

Resolution: 1

Gain A:

B:

Notes:

DRS time	Flight ptrn	Filename	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Mir.	Det.	Win	Macro(s)	Gain		Comments
										A	B	
082153	Pre-flight	B173b	C	N23	N21	18	-190	20	CH1x1	2	2	OK
082923	-	B173c	C	N23	N21	19	-190	19	CH2x1	2	2	OK
083128	-	B173D	C	24	N21	19	-190	19	N1x1	2	2	OK
083251	-	B173E	C	24	N22	19	-190	20	Z1x1	2	2	OK
0834N	-	B173F	C	24	22	19	-190	20	Z1x1	2	2	OK
083537	-	B173E	C	24	22	19	-190	20	1Rx1	2	2	OK
0849	T/O											
082119	P2	B173I	O	66	32	17	-191	26	CH1x2	2	2	OK
103248	R1 ^{500'} 100'	B173J	C	71	31	20	-191	27	CH1x1	2	2	EP2/turn
103406	100'	B173K	C	71	31	21	-190		"	2	2	OK
103515	R1,100'	B173L	O	71	31	21	-191	27	Z1x3	2	2	
103804	"	B173M	C	71	31	23	-191	27	CH1x1	2	2	
103913	"	B173N	O	71	31	23	-191	27	Z1x3	2	2	
104204	"	B173O	C	71	32	24	-190	27	CH1x1	2	2	
104312	"	B173P	C	71	31	24	-191	27	N1x3	2	2	TAT 17.7
104608	"	Q	C						CH1	2	2	
1047N	"	R	C						N1x1	2	2	
10	"	S	C	71	31	24	-191	28	N1x2	2	2	EdR N 2/3
105644	2500'R2	V	C						CH1x1			OK

ARIES flight log

Flight: *B173*

Location: *N of Dakan*

page 2 of 4

Date: *14-2-6*

Operator(s): *VANCE*

Resolution:

Gain A: *2* B: *2*

Notes:

DRS time	Flight ptrn	Filename	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Mir.	Det.	Win	Macro(s)	Comments	
<i>105745</i>	<i>B173 W</i>	<i>B173W</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>71</i>	<i>31</i>	<i>23</i>	<i>-190</i>	<i>28</i>	<i>N1X3</i>		
<i>110032</i>	<i>R2</i>	<i>B173X</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>71</i>	<i>31</i>	<i>23</i>	<i>-191</i>	<i>28</i>	<i>CH1X1</i>		
<i>110040</i>	↓	<i>B173Y</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>71</i>	<i>31</i>	<i>22</i>	<i>-191</i>	<i>28</i>	<i>N1X3</i>		
<i>110425</i>		<i>B173Z</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>71</i>	<i>31</i>	<i>22</i>	<i>-191</i>	<i>28</i>	<i>CH1X1</i>		
<i>1106~</i>		<i>B173φ</i>	<i>O</i>						<i>Z1X2</i>		
<i>110756</i>		<i>B1731</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>71</i>	<i>31</i>	<i>21</i>	<i>-191</i>	<i>27</i>	<i>CH1X1</i>		
<i>110907</i>		<i>B1732</i>	<i>O</i>	<i>70</i>	<i>31</i>	<i>22</i>	<i>-191</i>	<i>27</i>	<i>Z1X2</i>		
<i>111111</i>	↓	<i>B1733</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>71</i>	<i>31</i>	<i>21</i>	<i>-191</i>	<i>27</i>	<i>CH1X1</i>		
<i>111505</i>	<i>R3</i>	<i>B1734</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>71</i>	<i>31</i>	<i>21</i>	<i>-191</i>	<i>28</i>	<i>CH1X1</i>		
<i>111611</i>	↓	<i>B1735</i>	<i>O</i>	<i>70</i>	<i>31</i>	<i>20</i>	<i>-191</i>	<i>27</i>	<i>Z1X3</i>		
<i>111903</i>		<i>B1736</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>71</i>	<i>31</i>	<i>20</i>	<i>-190</i>	<i>26</i>	<i>CH1X1</i>		
<i>112010</i>		<i>B1737</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>71</i>	<i>31</i>	<i>20</i>	<i>-190</i>	<i>27</i>	<i>N1X3</i>		
<i>112258</i>		<i>B1738</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>71</i>	<i>31</i>	<i>20</i>	<i>-190</i>	<i>27</i>	<i>CH1X1</i>		
<i>112421</i>		↓	<i>B1739</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>71</i>	<i>31</i>				<i>N1X2</i>	
<i>113020?</i>	<i>R4</i>	<i>B173a</i> <i>C173a</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>71</i>	<i>31</i>	<i>20</i>	<i>-190</i>	<i>28</i>	<i>CH1X1</i>		
<i>11~</i>	↓	<i>C173B</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>71</i>	<i>31</i>	<i>21</i>	<i>-191</i>	<i>28</i>	<i>N1X3</i>		
<i>113400</i>		<i>C173C</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>71</i>	<i>31</i>	<i>21</i>	<i>-191</i>	<i>28</i>	<i>N1X1</i>		
<i>113506</i>		<i>C173D</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>70</i>	<i>31</i>	<i>21</i>	<i>-191</i>	<i>28</i>	<i>CH1X1</i>		
<i>113630</i>		↓	<i>C173E</i>	<i>O</i>	<i>70</i>	<i>31</i>	<i>21</i>	<i>-190</i>	<i>27</i>	<i>Z1X4</i>	

FOR 112456

ARIES flight log

Flight: B173

Location: N of Dahan

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Date: 14-2-6

Operator(s): VANCE

Resolution:

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Notes:

DRS time	Flight ptrn	Filename	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Mir.	Det.	Win	Macro(s)	Comments
114004	R4, 4000'	C173F	C	71	31	22	-190	27	CHIX1	
114118?	"	C173G	O	70	31	22	-191	27	ZIX1	
114235?	"	C173H	●C						ZIX1	OOPS
114343	"	C173I	C	71	31	23	-190	28	CHIX1	(1143 EOR)
1147	Restarting for file handles									
115747	R5500'	C173J							CHIX1	
11558	"	C173L	71	31	31	23	-190	29	ZIX1 NIX5	120119 EOR
120358	R6	C173M	C			OK			CHIX1	
120847		C173N							NIX3	
121209		C173O							CHIX1	
121209		C173P				OK			NIX3	
121353		C173Q							CHIX1	Vance 1. procedure open size 0.
12153		C173R	✓						NIX3	
1218		C173S				OK			CHIX1	
125117		C173T				OK			CHIX1	
125130		C173U							NIX5	
125130		C173V UW							CHIX1	
1259~		C173W							ZIX5	
130339		C173X	✓						CHIX1	

ARIES flight log

Flight: B173

Location: N of Dakan

page 4 of 4

Date: 14-2-6

Operator(s): VANCE

Resolution: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Notes: ... this is no way to spend Valentines day!

DRS time	Flight ptrn	Filename	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Mir.	Det.	Win	Macro(s)	Comments
1305)		C173 Y	0						21x5	
		C173 Z							CH(x)	
									Ladies & gentlemen,	
										We apologise for the
										failings in this log, both in terms of its
										incomplete nature up to and including
										file C173Z and for the utter absence of paper
										logging after that. This is due to a physiological
										operation malfunction. The only data not
										recorded in the .hsk files is the state of the
										shutter.
										We hope that the process of analysing these
										data are less painful than the process of
										recording them.

SWS and SHIMS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight #	B173	Date	14/02/06	Operat or(s)	Ian Rule	log page	1	of	1
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Note to operator: Indicate whether entry refers to SWS or SHIMS

Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Mirr Pos	Int Times		Remarks	S W S	U S H	L S H
				Vis	NIR				

Note: SWS on rack pc, SHIMS on laptop

094955	P1					T/o Dakar			
095321	P1		Zen+6 fwd	75	250	SWS running	x		
095751	P1			75	250	SHIMS running		x	
100030						Shutters closed for 15s, box temp =19			
100859	P1	FL190				End profile			
101015	P2	FL190				Start profile, cloud above			
102330						Shutters closed for 15s, box temp = 18			
103253		50'				End Profile			
103452	R1	100'	Zen +6fwd	75	250	Start run, cloud above	x		
1034				75	250			x	
104200	R1		Nad+6aft	75	250	Shutters closed , sws mirror moved	x		
104240			Nad +6 aft			Shutters open	X		
104358			Nad+6 aft	200	500	New integ times	x		
1044	R1	100'		75	250			X	
104952						End run, shutters closed			
105131	P3	100'	Zen+6 fwd	200	500	Start profile, shutters open	x		
105621	R2	2500'	Nad+6 aft	75	250	End profile, start run, shutters closed, sws integ time changed			
105837	R2	2500'	Nad+6 aft	200	500	Sws integ times changed	x		
1059				75	250			x	
110300	R2	2500	Zen+6 fwd	75	250	Shutters closed, mirror moved, integ time changed			
1104	R2	2500'		75	250			x	
111125						End run, close shutters			
111308	P4		Zen+6 fwd	75	250	Start profile	X		
111454	R3	4000'		75	250	End profile start run		x	
112200	R3	4000'	Nad+6 aft	200	500	Close shutters, move mirror, change sws integ times	x		
1122				75	250			x	
112456						End run			
1127						Shutters closed			
112755	P5	4000'	Nad+6 aft	200	500	Sws pointing down, start profile	x		
113010	R4	2500'		75	250	End profile, start run		x	
114353						End run,			
114427	P6.1	2500				Start P6.1			
114652	P6.2	500'				End profile, start next			
1149				75	250		x		
1149				75	250			x	
115059	P6.3	5000'				End profile start next, cloudy above			
115606	P6.4	500'				End profile, start next			
115711	R5	1500'	Nad+6aft	75	250	End profile, start run	X		
1158	R5	1500'		75	250			x	
115945	R5					Shutters closed for 15s			
120119						End run, shutters closed			
120309	P7	1500'				Start profile			
120429	R6.1	500				End profile, start run, box temp = 20			
121144						Interrupt run, shutters closed			
121238	R6.2	1500'				Restart run			

Bags are numbers 1-140 and tubes are the other samples

<i>Date</i>	<i>14/02/06</i>	<i>Tubes & Bags</i>		<i>Flight#</i>	<i>B173</i>		
T.O.	09:49:53	Land	14:36:33	04:46:40			Jim McQuaid (ULeeds)
Tube/Bag #	START	END	Alt. (ft)	Sample Time	Flow	Vol	Comments
24619	10:37:50	10:47:30	100	00:09:40	300	2900	tube appears to be restricted in some way
67687	10:57:45	11:09:50	2300	00:12:05	250	3021	
62135	11:14:52	11:21	4000	00:06:08	350	2147	
67629	11:22	11:28:10	4000	00:06:10	350	2158	
62182	11:32:14	11:39	2500	00:06:46	300	2030	
67634	11:30	11:41:30	n/a	00:11:30	300	3450	BLANK
62160	11:59:30	12:12	????	00:12:30	300	3750	
67641	12:57:40	13:09	1500	00:11:20	250	2833	
62196	13:11:50	13:21	1500	00:09:40	250	2417	
62379	13:26:20	13:38:40	13:38:40	00:12:20	300	3700	

WAS Filling Log				
Operator - Jim McQuaid				
Date	Bottle#	Start	End	Comments
14/02/2006	36	10:38:51	10:39:51	bottles in case 5 not purged
14/02/2006	37	10:42:55	10:43:55	bottles in case 5 not purged
14/02/2006	38	10:48:07	10:49:07	bottles in case 5 not purged
14/02/2006	39	10:58:47	10:59:47	bottles in case 5 not purged
14/02/2006	40	11:03:06	11:04:07	
14/02/2006	25	11:08:03	11:09:03	
14/02/2006	26	11:18:51	11:19:51	
14/02/2006	27	11:23:38	11:24:38	
14/02/2006	28	11:27:35	11:28:35	
14/02/2006	29	11:33:02	11:34:02	
14/02/2006	30	11:37:39	11:38:39	
14/02/2006	31	11:40:27	11:41:27	
14/02/2006	16	12:56:00	12:57:00	
14/02/2006	17	12:58:21	12:59:22	
14/02/2006	18	13:03:39	13:04:39	
14/02/2006	19	13:09:24	13:10:24	
14/02/2006	20	13:26:29	13:27:29	
14/02/2006	21	13:31:21	13:32:21	
14/02/2006	32	13:34:35	13:35:35	

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B 173** Date: 14th February 2006

Instrument	Operated	Instrument	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>		<u>Cloud Physics</u>	
INU	N	Probes	
XR5M GPS	Y	FFSSP	Y
Cruciform GPS	N	PCASP	Y
Satcom C	Y	2D-P	Y
Satcom H	Y	2D-C	Y
<u>Thermometers</u>		Cloudscope	N
De-Iced Temp	Y	SID 1	Y
Non De-Iced	Y	SID 2	Y
Heimann	Y	HVPS	N
<u>Hygrometers</u>		CIP25	N
G. Eastern	Y	CIP100	Y
J. Williams	N		
Nevzorov	Y		
TWC	Y		
FWVS	N	Racks:	
<u>Radiometers</u>		INC	N
Upper Clear	Y	CCN / CPC	Y
“ Red	Y	CVI	Y
“ Silicon	Y		
“ SHIMS	Y	<u>Aerosol</u>	
Lower Clear	Y	PSAP	N
“ Red	Y	Nephelometer	Y
“ Silicon	Y	Filters	Y
		AMS	Y
<u>Large Radiometers</u>			
TAFTS	N		
MARSS	N		
DEIMOS	N	<u>Others:</u>	
ARIES	Y	NIR TDLAS	N
SWS	Y	2BT O3	N
<u>Chemistry</u>		VACC	Y
Ozone	Y	PEROXIDE	N
SO2	Y	Formaldehyde	N
NOX	Y	ADA	N
CO	Y	CPI	N
ORAC	N	NOxy	N
PAN	Y	PTRMS	N
PERCA	N	Bag Sampling	N
WAS	Y	Tube Sampling	Y

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B173

Date: 14 February 2006

Instruments

1. JW not operated
- 2.
- 3.
- 4.

Aircraft

Nil

Satcom Calls

Nil

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B173:

Log	Reason
Wet Nephelometer	No log as the instrument had too many problems for reliable data
Core Chemistry	pre flight only, unmanned operation on auto calibrate so no In Flight log
CVI	No log is ever taken for CVI
AMS	Log only of interest to instrument operator so no copy left with FAAM
VACC	No log is taken/provided for VACC
PAN	No log is taken/provided for PAN

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

3 x forward Facing Cameras
3 x Up/Downward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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